

22IEM06 S-CALe Up

D2

Paper submitted to a peer-reviewed journal on a quantum yield prediction model for induced junction photodiodes with targeted uncertainties better than 0.1 % from 250 nm to 400 nm, 0.2 % from 200 nm to 250 nm, and 0.01 % from 400 nm to 550 nm

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Deliverable Cover Sheet

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1 Summary

This deliverable reports on the development and validation of a quantum yield prediction model for induced-junction silicon photodiodes.

Quantum yield (QY) of a photodiode is defined as the ratio between the number of generated electron-hole pairs to the number of absorbed photons. QY is one of the major key parameters of photodiodes that must be accurately known when they are to be used as a primary detector standards, so called Predictable Quantum Efficient Detectors (PQEDs).

The essential steps for simulating the QY of silicon have been thoroughly studied within the wavelength range from 200 nm to 480 nm. Using Quantum Espresso software, we have estimated the contributions arising from primary carriers created after photon absorption separately. This was achieved by calculating the distribution functions of charge carriers over the available energy range, as well as the probabilities of charge carriers generating secondary carriers.

To validate the modelled quantum yield QY_{model} , we produced induced-junction silicon photodiodes and set up detectors equipped with these photodiodes. High-accuracy measurements of the spectral responsivity $R(\lambda)$ (referred to as $s(\lambda)$ in paper 2 part of this Deliverable) were performed using a cryogenic electrical substitution radiometer. Furthermore, we modelled the internal recombination losses $\delta(\lambda)$ [see Deliverable 1] and measured the reflectance $\rho(\lambda)$ of the same detectors at specific wavelengths, as a basis for modelling the reflectance over the wavelength range 200 nm to 480 nm. The following fundamental equation was used for validation, incorporating the aforementioned, derived key parameters and the fundamental constants elementary charge e , vacuum speed of light c and Planck's constant h :

$$QY_{\text{meas}} = \frac{R(\lambda) \cdot h \cdot c}{e \cdot \lambda \cdot (1 - \delta(\lambda)) \cdot (1 - \rho(\lambda))}$$

The comparison between QY_{model} and QY_{meas} indicates relative agreement of better than $\pm 1\%$ down to 300 nm and better than $\pm 2.5\%$ down to 200 nm. However, the deliverable is only partially fulfilled, as the target uncertainties have not been met. The reason for this is that the key photodiode parameters QY and internal recombination losses $\delta(\lambda)$ have been derived independently for the first time and within a very short period of only a few months for the UV wavelength range, as UV-irradiation stable photodiodes for wavelengths down to 200 nm were only available at the beginning of 2026. The QY modelling is made from first principles. In addition, accurate reflectance calculations are also needed to confirm the QY model. The high reflectance and its sensitivity to passivation thickness gave inconsistent data to work with early in the project.

This is also the reason that the submission of this deliverable is delayed. As it focuses on the wavelength range down to 200 nm, the above-mentioned validation of the quantum yield model requires working and UV-hard induced-junction photodiodes. The development of these photodiodes within the project took longer than expected, resulting in a significant delay of D2.

The above-mentioned agreement between modelling and validation measurements proves the meaningfulness of the derived values. However, improvements to the modelling will take more time and might result in even better agreement with the validation measurements.

2 Attachments

2.1 Paper 1: Quantum yield of Silicon in the UV-VIS spectral range

Journal Title

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Quantum yield of Silicon in the UV-VIS spectral range

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Toomas Kübarsepp^{1*}, Meelis-Mait Sildoja¹, Jaanus Vahi¹, Aarre Kilpeläinen², Farshid Manoocheri², Peter Meindl³, Tobias Pohl³, Lutz Werner³, Marek Šmid⁴, Geiland Porrovecchio⁴, Trinh Tran⁵, Jarle Gran⁵, and Erkki Ikonen^{2,6}

REVISED
dd Month Year¹AS Metrosert, Tallinn, Estonia²Aalto University, Metrology Research Institute, Espoo, Finland³Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt, Berlin, Germany⁴Czech Metrology Institute, Prague, Czech Republic⁵Justervesenet, Kjeller, Norway⁶VTI MIKES, Espoo, FinlandACCEPTED
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*Author to whom any correspondence should be addressed.

E-mail: toomas.kubarsepp@metrosert.ee

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Abstract

The essential steps for simulating quantum yield of Silicon have been thoroughly studied in the wavelength range from 200 nm to 480 nm. We have estimated separately excess quantum yield contributions arising from primary carriers created after photon absorption by using Quantum Espresso software. This is done by calculating distribution functions of charge carriers over available energy range and probabilities of charge carriers to generate secondary carriers. The resulting quantum yield values are compared to those of obtained by using the high-accuracy measurement data of different types of Silicon-based Predictable Quantum Efficient Detectors (PQED) indicating better than to $\pm 2.5\%$ relative agreement within spectral interval from 200 nm to 476 nm.

1. Introduction

The advances in optical technologies need continuous improvement of metrological methods and standards for a wide range of application areas. In optical measurements, semiconductor photodetectors are strong candidates for absolute standard detectors owing to low uncertainty, compact size and reasonable cost. In the visible and near infrared wavelength range, the new type of absolute photodetectors – Predictable Quantum Efficient Photodetector (PQED) based on special Silicon photodiodes has been demonstrated to be stable possessing predictable responsivity with extremely low uncertainty [1, 2, 3]. Extending PQED applications awaken need for physically justified model of quantum yield of Silicon which exceeds unity in the ultraviolet spectral range.

Over decades, several research groups have made efforts to derive from first principles the number of excess charge carriers after absorption of a photon [4, 5, 6, 7]. The attempts to elaborate a model for quantum yield in Silicon over wide spectral range were hampered by simplifications, e.g. parabolic band structure, equal distribution of excess kinetic energy between electrons and holes, and/or lack of accurate measurement data to compare with. In recent years, the research work on the elaboration of physically sound model for quantum yield of Silicon has been re-activated [8, 9] owing to improved measurement methods and facilities providing new and accurate responsivity measurement results [10]. The focus has been on calculation and prediction of the quantum yield in Silicon exceeding unity after absorption of a photon with sufficient energy. Yet again, simplified interpolation functions have been elaborated targeting ease-of-use of the quantum yield in spectral responsivity calculations in the UV-wavelength range.

Many earlier simplifying assumptions can be overcome using modern tools for band structure analysis and optical properties calculation. In the current work, we describe methods for Silicon excess quantum yield modeling from first principles and present calculation results by using open-source software Quantum Espresso (QE) [11]. We compare our model to the values derived from high-accuracy measured spectral responsivity recently became available. Also, we discuss our proposed model for excess quantum yield and further opportunities for improvement.

2. Method

To evaluate excess quantum yield in Silicon, $y(h\nu)-1$, we have used an approach describing contributions arising separately from carriers created after photon absorption event [4]:

$$y(h\nu) - 1 = \int dE [N_c(E)P_c(h\nu, E) + N_v(E)P_v(h\nu, E)] \quad (1)$$

where $h\nu$ is photon energy, $N_c(E)$ and $N_v(E)$ are the average numbers of carrier pairs created by impact ionization caused by a primary electron and hole, respectively. The symbols $P_c(h\nu, E)$ and $P_v(h\nu, E)$ denote distributions of electrons and holes, respectively, over excess kinetic energy E after the absorption of photon. The integration is performed over available kinetic energy E .

To evaluate both, average numbers of carrier pairs and distribution functions of primary carriers generated due to photon absorption, the band structure of Silicon has to be known. There are several methods from first principles to calculate band structure [12]. We have used pseudopotential method offered by open-source Quantum Espresso (QE) framework with self-consistent calculations within Density-Functional Theory (DFT) and applying a Projector-Augmented Wave-type (PAW) pseudopotential [11], which has been investigated by other research groups, e.g. [13, 14], and is being constantly improved in terms of physical aspects, as well as computational accuracy and speed [15]. However, due to well-known DFT band gap problem [16], QE recalculates the Fermi energy when performing the non self-consistent calculation and this could lead to band gap variations from 0.5 eV to 0.64 eV for Silicon rather than experimentally derived value of 1.123 eV. Although in optical transitions only energy difference in between valence and conduction bands matters, care should be taken to follow the Fermi energy used and reported during QE calculations to properly locate top of the uppermost valence band for correct carrier energy counting. In our calculations, we have used Fermi energy $E_F=6.505$ eV provided by QE and corrected the obtained calculated indirect band gap value 0.640 eV rigidly by 0.483 eV. In the present paper, we count energy of holes from the uppermost valence band and energy of electrons from the lowest conductance band, unless mentioned otherwise.

2.1. Energy distribution functions of primary carriers $P_i(E)$

The distribution functions of electrons $P_c(h\nu, E)$ and holes electrons $P_v(h\nu, E)$ over kinetic energy E are obtained by using linear-analytic-tetrahedron-method (LATM) [17]. The idea of the LATM is to subdivide the volume of integration into tetrahedral micro cells where wavevector k and energy E are determined exactly at the corners. It is then assumed that k and E vary linearly between the corners, after which the integral over each micro cell may be carried out analytically [18]. To do this, the volume integral is rewritten as a surface integral over surfaces of constant energy in the Brillouin Zone, making the integral independent of the shape of the cell. The contribution from each tetrahedron is then calculated and added

together, to get the result for the entire Irreducible Brillouin Zone (IBZ). The IBZ sub-mesh that we used consists of 256 tetrahedra.

This method effectively turns line integral in two-dimensional Brillouin Zone into a sum of analytic expressions that require only energy values at k -points at the vertices of tetrahedra. The calculation method by LATM includes transition matrix elements at the vertices of

tetrahedra. In the calculations, we have used equal transition matrix elements based on constant-matrix-element approximation [19].

The calculations of the distribution functions $P_i(h\nu, E)$ have been performed over interval of kinetic energy $0 < E < h\nu - E_g$, available for a generated carrier after absorption of a photon with energy $h\nu$. The index $i=c, v$ denotes electron or hole, respectively. The symbol $E_g=1.123$ eV stands for band gap of Silicon.

Quantum Espresso provides energy values at user specified k -points for calculation of the distribution functions $P_i(h\nu, E)$. We calculated the normalized distribution functions for electrons $P_c(h\nu, E)$ and holes $P_v(h\nu, E)$ separately and examples of distribution functions at some photon wavelengths are illustrated in Fig. 1. In general, it can be observed that kinetic energy is more likely distributed to created electrons at low photon energy. As photon energy increases, the excess kinetic energy is re-distributed between created electrons and holes.

2.2. Average numbers of carrier pairs $N_i(E)$

The average numbers of carrier pairs $N_i(E)$ can be calculated as [20]:

$$N_i(E) = \left[1 + \frac{r'_i(E)}{r_i(E)} \right]^{-1} \quad (2)$$

where the index $i=c, v$ denotes electron or hole, respectively, $r'_i(E)$ is electron (or hole)-phonon scattering rate. The symbol $r_i(E)$ stands for electron (or hole) impact ionization rate. The average number of carrier pairs $N_i(E)$ according to Eq(2) is valid only if primary particle with energy E will decay to zero energy without ionization scattering or will be origin of one impact ionization event.

In several studies on quantum yield modeling [6, 7, 8, 9] both, the carrier-phonon scattering rate and impact ionization rate estimation trace back to pioneering work described in [20]. However, Alig et al derived the rates based on parabolic and isotropic band structure, which is not always the case for Silicon [21]. Furthermore, scattering rates and impact ionization rates were treated equal for electrons and holes.

Later research has shown that both, the impact ionization rates [22, 23] and the phonon scattering rates are different for electrons and holes [13, 14].

For electrons, we adopted simulation method for the impact ionization rate described in [22] and recently confirmed by experiments [24]. According to this method, the impact ionization rate for electrons in units 1/s can be calculated as:

$$r_c(E) = 1 \cdot 10^{11} \cdot (E - \varepsilon_c)^{4.6} \quad (3)$$

where E is electron energy in units eV and $\varepsilon_c=1.1$ eV. The above Eq(3) for practical use was obtained by least-square-fitting to the numerical Monte Carlo simulation results of impact

ionization rate of electrons in Silicon derived from wave functions and band structure based on an empirical pseudopotential method.

In the calculations of the impact ionization rate in units 1/s for holes, we use the method showing similar shape as for electrons, yet with different values of parameters:

$$r_v(E) = 2 \cdot 10^{12} \cdot (E - \varepsilon_v)^{4.0} \quad (4)$$

where E is hole energy in units eV and $\varepsilon_v=1.6$ eV. The parameter values in Eq(4) for practical use were obtained by least-square-fitting to the numerical Monte Carlo simulation results of impact ionization rate of holes in Silicon [23].

We use previously published carrier-phonon scattering rates obtained with the help of QE [13]. The theoretical framework and calculation details are given in [13], nevertheless, we corrected the band gap of Silicon to $E_g=1.123$ eV as depicted in Fig. 2.

By combining the carrier-phonon scattering rates $r_i'(E)$ and impact ionization rates $r_i(E)$, we obtained average numbers of carrier pairs $N_i(E)$ (Fig 3) using Eq(2). For illustration purposes, the rates of electron-phonon scattering and hole-phonon scattering are embedded. As can be seen, the baselines of average numbers $N_i(E)$ are closely guided by the carrier impact ionization

rates $r_i(E)$. This is expected, because carrier-phonon scattering rates $r_i'(E)$ are less energy dependent (Fig. 2) as compared to that of impact ionization rates of both, electrons and holes.

Also, we notice that the average number of electrons $N_c(E)$ and holes $N_v(E)$ are different.

3. Results

Using Eq(1) to integrate the estimated average numbers of carrier pairs $N_i(E)$ and the distribution functions of carriers $P_i(h\nu, E)$ over appropriate limits determined by excess energy E , the expected excess of quantum yield $y(h\nu)-1$ of Silicon is obtained (Fig. 4). Over the wavelength range from 200 nm to 480 nm the calculation step of excess quantum yield is 5 nm. The actual cut-off of the modeled excess quantum yield is at about 479.3 nm-wavelength owing to the Fermi energy $E_F=6.505$ eV we used in the calculations of carrier distribution functions $P_i(h\nu, E)$.

We compare the modeled excess quantum yield to the accurate values obtained using special type of photodetectors – Predictable Quantum Efficient Photodetectors (PQED) composed of stable Silicon-based photodiodes. The PQED photodiodes are induced-junction photodiodes made of high purity silicon wafer doped by about $2 \cdot 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and passivated by either thermally grown SiO_2 without [1, 2] or with plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposited (PECVD) SiN_x thin film on top of thermally grown SiO_2 -layer [24]. The relationship between the responsivity of semiconductor photodetector, losses (internal quantum deficiency and reflectance) and quantum yield can be found elsewhere, e.g. [8, 9]. In such a way, the quantum yield values have been derived in [8, 9, 25, 26] and we used the same method estimating the

losses [27] to obtain values of quantum yield from high-accuracy measured responsivity data described in [28]. The comparison results are presented in Figs 4 and 5.

The good agreement between the modeled and measured values of excess quantum yield $y(h\nu)-1$ can be noticed over the studied range of photon energy. Some increase in discrepancy between the modelled and measured values can be observed at low photon energies below 3.0 eV. On the other hand, the uncertainty in the modeled values is high at low photon energies, which is discussed in Section 4.

When comparing quantum yield of Silicon, i.e. $y(h\nu)$, the agreement in relative terms between the modeled and measured values is better than to $\pm 2.5\%$ with the standard deviation of approximately 0.9% in the wavelength range from 200 nm to 476 nm (Fig. 5).

4. Discussion

The calculation of excess quantum yield according to Eq (1) involves number of parameters which are determined based on theoretical frameworks, semi-empirical considerations and measurement results. The parameters are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. List of parameters used in excess quantum yield calculations using Equation 1.

Parameter	Equation	Value	Reference	Variation
Fermi energy (eV)	(1), (2)	6.505	[11]	± 0.150 eV
Multiplication factor (1/s)	(3)	$1 \cdot 10^{11}$	[22]	$\pm 10\%$
Threshold ε_c (eV)	(3)	1.1	[22]	$\pm 10\%$
Exponent	(3)	4.6	[22, 25]	$\pm 2\%$
Multiplication factor (1/s)	(4)	$2 \cdot 10^{12}$	[23]	$\pm 10\%$
Threshold ε_v (eV)	(4)	2.0	[23]	$\pm 10\%$
Exponent	(4)	4.0	[23]	$\pm 2\%$

The Fermi energy is recalculated when Quantum Espresso performs the non self-consistent calculation and this could lead to variations by about ± 0.15 eV. We have conducted calculations of excess quantum yield and estimated that the relative change can be about 6% at photon energy 6.2 eV and about 40% at photon energy 2.6 eV in the excess quantum yield. At low photon energy values, the relative change seems to be huge; on the other hand, the modeled excess quantum yield is small, e.g. $y(h\nu) - 1 = 130$ ppm at photon energy of 2.6 eV.

In addition, knowing Fermi energy is important when studying real photodiode structures as Fermi energy can change due to semiconductor doping [21]. This may increase concentration of electrons in conductance band minimum ready to receive excess kinetic energy. The Fermi energy can depend on electric field in a photodiode, as well, introducing further challenges in calculations of excess quantum yield. The knowledge about exact estimates of quantum yield in real photodiode structures is still to be improved.

In the calculations of carrier distribution function $P_i(h\nu, E)$ we have used resolution of 0.01 eV to optimize the calculation speed. The corresponding wavelength resolution can be up to 2 nm at longer light wavelengths. Introducing higher resolution may increase calculation accuracy, especially at around photon wavelengths at which quantum yield becomes to exceed unity.

The calculation of carrier impact ionization rates $r_i(E)$ includes parameters whose values are obtained by least-square-fitting to the first-principle numerical simulations [22, 23]. The estimated variation intervals of those parameter values are listed in Table 1. The corresponding relative variation in excess quantum yield is 10%, almost uniform in the wavelength range studied.

Last but not least, the carrier-phonon scattering rates are adopted from previously published data [13]. The resolution of 0.001 eV has been used in those calculations, while we extract data with resolution of 0.01 eV needed to match the resolution of carrier distribution

function $P_i(h\nu, E)$. Although, integration over energy interval diminishes the influence arising from difference between calculation and extraction resolution of the carrier-phonon scattering rates, the contribution to the relative variation in excess quantum yield could span from 3% at 200-nm photon wavelength to about 30% at 479-nm photon wavelength.

By combining the variation of the parameters listed in Table 1, the variation of excess quantum yield is estimated and illustrated by dashed lines in Fig. 4. In relative terms, the variation in excess quantum yield is about 20% almost uniform up to the wavelength of 410 nm and increases to 50% at the wavelength of 479 nm. In absolute terms, the variation is 0.100 at 200-nm photon wavelength and gradually decreases to 0.00030 at 479-nm photon wavelength. At those wavelengths, the modeled excess quantum yield is 0.570 and 0.00013, respectively.

The modeled and measured excess quantum yield exhibits slightly complicated structure above photon energy of 4 eV peaking at about 4.32 eV (Fig. 4). This phenomenon has been previously related to pronounced contribution by holes [6].

At photon energy 4.32 eV we calculated carrier distribution functions $P_i(h\nu, E)$ (Fig. 6) and found that there is a clear peak in the distribution of electrons at maximum kinetic energy. In conjunction with average number of carrier pairs created by electrons $N_c(E)$, the electron distribution function $P_c(h\nu, E)$ makes higher contribution to the excess quantum yield as compared to that of holes. This can be supported by referring to Silicon band structure where many carrier pairs are generated in direct transitions around Γ_2' -point giving the major fraction of the excess kinetic energy to the electrons.

The modeled excess quantum yield of Silicon shows a small dip around the photon energy of 4.62 eV ($\lambda=268$ nm) (Fig. 4). As we notice, there is analogous decrease in average number of carrier pairs created by electrons $N_c(E)$ close to this photon energy. In the same situation, no significant re-distribution of energy is observed between the functions $P_c(h\nu, E)$ and $P_v(h\nu, E)$ (Fig. 6). By referring to Silicon band structure, it can be explained by absorption of a photon with energy around 4.62 eV resulting mostly in indirect transitions, which causes increased probability for carrier-phonon scattering.

5. Conclusions

The quantum yield of Silicon has been studied and model derived from first principles in the wavelength range from 200 nm to 480 nm. We found it useful to calculate separately contributions arising from primary electrons and holes generated after photon absorption. The probabilities of charge carriers over available kinetic energy range and probabilities of charge carriers to generate secondary carriers were estimated. We applied pseudopotential method available from open-source Quantum Espresso software platform.

Our calculations show that the distribution functions of electrons $P_c(h\nu, E)$ and holes $P_v(h\nu, E)$ over available kinetic energy $E=h\nu-E_g$ are not necessarily equal. For example, at low photon energy most of the excess kinetic energy is received by electrons. This can be useful to simplify calculation of excess quantum yield $y(h\nu)-1$ in the photon energy range from about 2.5 eV to 3.2 eV, i.e. including direct transitions at Γ -point, by relying on impact ionization initiated by electrons only as experimentally verified in [25]. On the other hand, at higher photon energy the separate handling of distribution functions of carriers assists to understand physical processes in Silicon.

The estimates of average number of carrier pairs $N_i(E)$ include the carrier-phonon scattering rates $r'_i(E)$ and impact ionization rates initiated $r_i(E)$ by primary carrier generated. We can support that in the calculations of the rates the realistic Silicon band structure has to be used.

Our modeled excess quantum yield of Silicon is compared to the values derived from high-accuracy measured spectral responsivity data [8, 9, 25, 26, 28]. The comparison shows that, in

absolute terms, the agreement is better than to ± 0.02 at the wavelength of 200 nm and about ± 0.0002 at the wavelength of 476 nm.

Nevertheless, there are several possibilities to improve accuracy of modeling, e.g. by increasing sub-mesh of Silicon irreducible Brillouin Zone, by using higher energy resolution in the calculations, and, when it comes to real photodiode structures, the effects of doping profile and induced electric field on quantum yield are useful to consider.

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2.2 Paper 2: Cryogenic-Radiometer-Based UV Spectral Responsivity Calibration and Temporal Stability Assessment of Induced-Junction Photodiodes

Cryogenic-Radiometer-Based UV Spectral Responsivity Calibration and Temporal Stability Assessment of Induced-Junction Photodiodes

Tobias Pohl¹, Peter Meindl¹, Ozhan Koybasi², Michael N. Getz², Eivind Bardalen³,
Meelis-Mait Sildoja⁴, Jarle Gran⁵, and Lutz Werner¹

¹Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB), Berlin, Germany

²SINTEF, Oslo, Norway

³University of South-Eastern Norway (USN), Borre, Norway

⁴Metrosert, Tallinn, Estonia

⁵Justervesenet (JV), Kjeller, Norway

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Abstract

The Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB) has updated one of its cryogenic electrical substitution radiometer facilities with a laser-driven light source for SI-traceable detector calibrations of the spectral responsivity in the UV wavelength range from 200 nm to 410 nm. Several detectors equipped with silicon photodiodes have been calibrated with relative standard measurement uncertainties of about 0.1% at this facility. These measurements have been performed in order to investigate the temporal stability of the photodiodes' spectral responsivity over a time frame of 2 months to about 2 years. Some photodiodes show significant degradation, whereas others are stable within the measurement uncertainty. The calibration of the spectral responsivity of these photodiodes furthermore provides the basis for evaluating their suitability for utilization as primary detector standards, so called Predictable Quantum Efficient Detectors (PQEDs).

1 Introduction

In the last decades, cryogenic electrical substitution radiometers (CESRs) have been the gold standard in primary reference measurement procedures for the measurement of radiant power in the ultraviolet (UV), visible (VIS) and infrared (IR) part of the spectrum [1] and thus for the calibration of radiation detectors in view of their spectral responsivity. The spectral responsivity $s(\lambda)$ describes the detector's electrical response - which is the photocurrent I_{ph} in case of a photodiode - on incident optical radiant power Φ of the wavelength λ :

$$s(\lambda) = \frac{I_{\text{ph}}}{\Phi} \quad (1)$$

However, operating a CESR is labour-intensive and requires considerable time, infrastructure and expertise. Therefore, the development of so-called self-calibrating photodiodes – also known as Predictable Quantum Efficient Detectors (PQEDs) – serving as primary detector standards could take absolute radiometry to the next level in terms of simplicity and availability of SI-traceable radiant power measurement: Accurate measurement and/or simulation

of photodiode key parameters enables to calculate the spectral responsivity $s_{\text{calc}}(\lambda)$ depending on the vacuum wavelength λ using the following fundamental equation:

$$s_{\text{calc}}(\lambda) = \frac{e \cdot \lambda}{h \cdot c} \cdot (1 - \rho(\lambda)) \cdot (1 - \delta(\lambda)) \cdot y(\lambda) \quad (2)$$

Eq. 2 is based on the fundamental constants elementary charge e , vacuum speed of light c and Planck’s constant h , along with the photodiode key parameters quantum yield y , reflectivity ρ and internal recombination losses δ [2].

Within the EMPIR 18SIB10 chipS·CALe [3] and EPM 22IEM06 S-CALe Up [4] projects, silicon photodiodes were fabricated and their aforementioned key parameters were determined for the first time in the UV and short VIS range [5, 6, 7, 8], enabling calculation of $s_{\text{calc}}(\lambda)$ according to Eq. 2. The above-mentioned projects focus on so-called induced-junction photodiodes, which exhibit reduced internal recombination losses that are easier to compute [9]. The majority of the studied photodiodes are therefore induced-junction photodiodes, as shown in Tab. 1 and 2. In addition, some externally doped photodiodes are included to provide comparability.

However, this approach of self-calibrating photodiode standards is only as accurate and feasible as

- their photodiode key parameters are once verified by accurate measurements against CESRs and
- the temporal stability of the photodiodes’ spectral responsivity is verified, as aging is a known problem of UV photodiodes [10, 11].

For these reasons, three-element reflection trap detectors have been set up with the aforementioned photodiodes, and their spectral responsivity $s_{\text{meas}}(\lambda)$ has been measured against PTB’s CCSR over a period of up to 22 months.

2 Set up of three-element reflection trap detectors and calibration scheme

The use of photodiodes in a three-element reflection trap design combines reduced reflection losses - achieved through multiple specular reflections (five in the present design) - with a spatially uniform detector response that is insensitive to the polarisation of the incident radiation [12].

PTB’s detector design is depicted in Fig. 1, which is equipped with an aperture with a nominal diameter of 8 mm, that can be replaced by an aperture as required by different measurement facilities. It provides individual readout of each of the three photodiodes or, via an adapter cable, parallel readout of all photodiodes. The detector’s temperature can be varied using liquid-based heat transfer through a metal hose, and monitored with the integrated Pt100 temperature sensor.

Tab. 1 lists the amount and type of studied photodiodes alongside the realised time frame and calibration wavelength range. The spectral step-width was typically 5 nm. Tab. 1 also specifies the wafer origin. Note that the wafers listed from the chipS·CALe project are nominally identical, whereas within the S-CALe Up project different wafers are fabricated differently. More detailed information on the photodiode fabrication process and layer structures can be found in Tab. 2 and [13, 14]. The photodiodes have a nominal sensitive area of 11 mm x 11 mm. They all have been packaged to match PTB’s detector design.

The TC1, TC2, TC3 and TC4 detectors, which are equipped with chipS·CALe photodiodes, were ready for measurement as early as June 2024. This enabled a temporal stability

Figure 1: Three-element reflection trap detector in partially section view (a). Orientation of the three photodiodes (depicted in orange), resulting in five reflections within the detector. Incident radiation is visualised in light red (b). Set-up of the detector (c).

Table 1: Overview of investigated photodiodes including the measurement time frame and calibration wavelength range. The detector name is PTB-given and will be used for identification purposes within this publication. Photodiodes named TC originate from the chipS-CALe project, while the S in the name indicates origin from the S-CALe Up project. Photodiodes from wafers marked with * are not induced-junction photodiodes, but externally doped, see Tab. 2 for more information. Measurements were usually conducted starting at the shorter wavelength and proceeding in 5 nm steps to the upper wavelength limit. However, the TC2 measurements marked with ** were each performed in two consecutive spectral intervals: The range from 300 nm to 410 nm was measured first, followed by the range from 200 nm to 300 nm.

Name	Wafer#	Calibration wavelength range / nm							
		2024 June	2025 June	2025 November	2026 February	2026 March	2026 April	2026 May	
TC1	15/15/17	300 - 410	300 - 410						
TC2	15/15/17	300 - 410	300 - 410		200 - 410**	200 - 410**			
TC3	20/17/20	280 - 410	280 - 410			280 - 410			280 - 410
TC4	20/20/15	280 - 410	280 - 410			280 - 410			280 - 410
TS1	10*			200 - 410					
TS2	13*			200 - 410		200 - 410			
TS3	41			200 - 410				200 - 410	
TS4	6*				200 - 410				
TS5	43				200 - 410				
TS6	44				200 - 410			200 - 410	

study to be conducted over a time period of almost two years, involving four consecutive measurements. However, pre-testing of these photodiodes revealed degradation due to UV irradiation below 280 nm. Therefore, these photodiodes were only measured at wavelengths equal or longer than 280 nm (TC1), and as a precaution, from 300 nm and above (TC3, TC4). TC2 was also only measured at wavelengths equal or longer than 280 nm in the first three rounds. However, in the 3rd and 4th round additional measurements down to 200 nm were performed with this detector despite the risk of UV-induced degradation. The results will be presented and discussed in Sect. 4.3.

Due to the time-consuming production process of the S-CALe Up photodiodes, the temporal stability of these photodiodes could only be studied over a time period of two months (TS6) to five months (TS3) to date.

TC1 was not measured a third time, and TS1, TS4 and TS5 were not measured a second time, in order to reduce calibration time and focus on the most promising detectors.

Table 2: Overview of investigated photodiodes and some of their fabrication details. For the passivation of some photodiodes, Plasma-Enhanced Chemical Vapor Deposition (PECVD) is applied. Photodiodes without an implant species are induced-junction photodiodes. For more information, see [14], however, some of the production details are confidential.

Name	Wafer#	Project	Passivation process	Implant species	Crystal orientation
TC1	15/15/17	chipS-CALe	6 nm thermal SiO ₂ ; deposit 65 nm PECVD SiN _x	None	Si(100)
TC2	15/15/17				
TC3	20/17/20				
TC4	20/20/15				
TS1	10	S-CALe Up	anneal at 900 °C for 10 min; leave 15 nm screening oxide; deposit 22 nm PECVD SiN _x	As	Si(100)
TS2	13		strip screening oxide; grow 15 nm SiO ₂ at 1000 °C; deposit 22 nm PECVD SiN _x	As	Si(100)
TS3	41		grow 15 nm SiO ₂ at 1000 °C; deposit 90 nm PECVD SiN _x	None	Si(111)
TS4	6		anneal at 900 °C for 10 min; leave 15 nm screening oxide; deposit 22 nm PECVD SiN _x ; etch oxide and PECVD SiN _x	Sb	Si(100)
TS5	43		grow thermal SiO ₂ only	None	Si(111)
TS6	44		grow thermal SiO ₂ ; perform a post-oxidation treatment for improved stability	None	Si(111)

3 Cryogenic electrical substitution radiometer

3.1 Updated facility

The UV spectral responsivity calibration and temporal stability assessment of the mentioned silicon photodiodes was conducted at a cryogenic electrical substitution radiometer (CESR) facility at PTB. CESRs are primary standards for the measurement of optical radiant power [1], and therefore provide SI-traceable calibration possibilities of radiation detectors' spectral responsivity $s(\lambda)$.

The PTB cryogenic electrical substitution radiometer [15, 16] comprises a radiant power absorber that is thermally coupled to a temperature-stabilized heat sink maintained slightly above the temperature of liquid helium. The absorber is electrically heated to a defined temperature slightly above that of the heat sink. When additional radiant power is absorbed, the electrical heating power must be reduced accordingly to keep the absorber at a constant temperature. This change in electrical heating power can be measured with low uncertainty and serves as a direct measure of the absorbed radiant power Φ_{CESR} , traceable to the PTB realizations of the electrical quantities voltage and resistance.

To prevent icing of the cavity due to water vapour in the air, the CESR is operated under vacuum. Since the rest of the measurement setup, such as the radiation sources and the detectors to be calibrated, is not operated under vacuum, an entrance window is required. This entrance window is made of fused silica and has a wedge angle of 3° to avoid interference effects.

A second, nominal identical wedged window is positioned in front of the detectors under

Figure 2: Typical radiant power at the CESR and the detector under test during calibration.

test to obtain a comparable beam path. Therefore, only the ratio F_{window} of the transmittances of the two nominal identical windows has to be measured for a correction of the spectral responsivity measurement at each calibration wavelength. The calibration took place at 25 °C laboratory and detector temperature, and a reverse bias voltage of 1 V was applied throughout.

A maximum of 3 detectors can be calibrated simultaneously against the CESR. A monitor photodiode is used to correct for temporal drifts in the radiant power level during the measurement process. The photocurrents of the monitor and detector under test are read out synchronously using two transimpedance amplifiers and two digital Agilent 3458A voltmeters. A shutter is used to correct for background signal drift.

Recently, this CESR facility at PTB was updated with a laser-driven light source (LDLS) of the type EQ-1500 from Energetiq Technology, Inc. as a broadband UV radiation source. Together with a prism and a grating monochromator combination, calibrations in the wavelength range from 200 nm to 410 nm with a spectral bandwidth of about 1 nm are enabled. The realized radiant power at the detector under test is depicted in Fig. 2.

3.2 Determination of the spectral responsivity

The spectral responsivity s_{meas} is determined according to Eq. 3. The quantities will be explained in the following.

$$s_{\text{meas}}(\lambda) = \frac{U_{\text{DUT}}}{R_{\text{TIA}}} \cdot \frac{U_{\text{Mon-CESR}}}{U_{\text{Mon-DUT}} \cdot \Phi_{\text{CESR}}} \cdot F \quad (3)$$

The photocurrent $I_{\text{ph,DUT}}$ of the detector under test (DUT) is measured as the voltage U_{DUT} with a transimpedance amplifier (TIA) with the feedback resistance R_{TIA} . Φ_{CESR} is the radiant power determined by the CESR.

The photocurrent of the monitor detector is measured as the voltage $U_{\text{Mon-DUT}}$ (synchronously measured with U_{DUT}) respectively $U_{\text{Mon-CESR}}$ (synchronously measured with Φ_{CESR}) with a second TIA. Its feedback resistance cancels out in Eq. 3, as $U_{\text{Mon-CESR}}$ and $U_{\text{Mon-DUT}}$ are measured with the same TIA. The correction factor F is the product of the following quantities, see also Tab. 4:

- F_{α} : Cavity absorptance of the CESR
- F_{window} : Wavelength dependent measured ratio of the window transmittances
- $F_{\Delta\lambda}$: Spectral bandwidth correction factor
- F_{O_2} : Correction factor due to oxygen absorption
- F_{SR} : Correction factor due to stray radiation
- F_{Φ} : Correction factor due to the electrical power measurement of the CESR

Figure 3: Typical relative standard measurement uncertainty, exemplarily shown for the first measurement with TS3.

- F_λ : Wavelength correction factor
- $F_{\text{non-uni}}$: Correction factor due to non-uniformity of the DUT’s spectral responsivity across the sensitive area and an uncertainty of the central detector position x_0 in the beam. Due to repeated detector positioning cycles, the estimated position uncertainty $u(x_0)$ is 0.2 mm. $u(F_{\text{non-uni}})$ is calculated by multiplying $u(x_0)$ by $\frac{\partial I_{\text{ph,rel}}}{\partial x}$, see Sect. 4.2.
- F_T : Correction factor due to temperature dependence of the DUT’s spectral responsivity

4 Measurement results

4.1 Measurement uncertainty

Firstly, the measurement uncertainty budget is presented in order to evaluate the UV spectral responsivity calibration and determine whether observed temporal instabilities are significant: In this publication, changes in spectral responsivity are considered insignificant when the absolute difference between repeated measurements does not exceed the standard measurement uncertainty of the individual measurements. A detector fulfilling this condition over the observation period is regarded as temporally stable.

The typical relative standard measurement uncertainty is exemplarily shown for the first measurement of TS3 in Fig. 3. It is in the order of 0.1 % for the wavelength range from 270 nm and above. Due to reduced radiant power below 270 nm, compare Fig. 2, the relative standard measurement uncertainty increases with shorter wavelengths up to about 0.8 %, since one of the major uncertainty contributions is type A uncertainty of the measured signals from the CESR and the detector under test. A full measurement uncertainty budget for two exemplarily chosen wavelengths is presented in Tab. 4.

4.2 Uniformity characterisation

The central detector position x_0 to which the detectors were aligned in the beam was found by scanning the detector in 0.5 mm steps and measuring the detector signal $I_{\text{ph}}(x)$ at each position x . These scans have been performed for all detector rotation angles at intervals of 30° . The obtained data provide information not only about the central detector position x_0 but also about the spatial distribution of the spectral responsivity across the detectors’ sensitive area, which is referred to here as ‘non-uniformity’. The beam has a wavelength-independent diameter of about 2.6 mm.

Figure 4: Relative measured detector signal $I_{\text{ph,rel}}$ in dependence of the detector position position x (blue). The red line depicts the linear fit $\frac{\partial I_{\text{ph,rel}}}{\partial x}$, corresponding to the values given in Tab. 3.

Tab. 3 lists the relative change of the detector signal $I_{\text{ph,rel}} = \frac{I_{\text{ph}}(x)}{I_{\text{ph,max}}}$ across the sensitive area. $\frac{\partial I_{\text{ph,rel}}}{\partial x}$ is calculated by applying a least square fit to the relative measured detector signals across the sensitive area. This fit is only performed on data points where the full beam is incident on the photodiodes and is not blocked by the aperture. If parabolic shapes appear in the detector signal scans that would lead to $\frac{\partial I_{\text{ph,rel}}}{\partial x_0} = 0$, the fit can be performed section-wise over data points $I_{\text{ph,rel}}(x)$ that follow a linear trend approximately. Fig. 4 shows exemplarily data for three of the detectors, which exhibit varying degrees of non-uniformity. The measurements were taken at 320 nm.

Due to poor uniformity of TS1 and TS4, these two detectors were excluded from the temporal stability assessment and will not be discussed here anymore. The remaining detectors, however, show excellent uniformity, where $u(F_{\text{non-uni}})$ is negligible.

Table 3: Non-uniformity of the detectors, given by the relative change of the detector signal across the sensitive area.

Detector name	$ \frac{\partial I_{\text{ph,rel}}}{\partial x} / \% \cdot \text{mm}^{-1}$
TC1	0.008
TC2	0.040
TC3	0.014
TC4	0.019
TS1	> 0.3
TS2	0.010
TS3	0.010
TS4	> 0.3
TS5	0.007
TS6	0.004

4.3 Spectral responsivity and its temporal stability

4.3.1 Spectral responsivity

Fig. 5 shows the spectral responsivity $s_{\text{meas}}(\lambda)$ as calibrated against the CESR for several of the set-up detectors and the spectral responsivity $s_{\text{calc}}(\lambda)$ according to Eq. 2 for the ideal case $\rho(\lambda) = \delta(\lambda) = 0$ and $y(\lambda) = 1$. The differences between $s_{\text{meas}}(\lambda)$ and $s_{\text{calc}}(\lambda)$, and the extent to which these can be explained by the simulation and measurement results of the

Figure 5: Measured spectral responsivity of the studied detectors and spectral responsivity of a so-called ideal photodiode with $s = e \cdot \lambda \cdot h^{-1} \cdot c^{-1}$, compare Eq. 2. For each detector, the first measurement performed as listed in Tab. 1 is shown. The measurement uncertainties are too small to be seen meaningfully, and are therefore not depicted, see Sect. 4.1.

photodiodes key parameters ρ , δ and y will be discussed comprehensively in [8]. The precise spectral responsivity calibrations allow the derived key parameters of the photodiodes to be validated independently. This validates whether the photodiodes can be used as primary detector standards.

However, it can be seen that TS2 and TS3 show almost identical spectral behaviour; as well as TS5 and TS6, which show almost identical spectral behaviour. Since TC1 to TC4 also show similar results with each other, only TC2 is depicted.

4.3.2 Temporal stability of TC1 to TC4

Fig. 6 shows a comparison of the spectral responsivity of detectors TC2 and TC3 over a time period of almost two years, with four consecutive measurements. Detector TC3 exhibits excellent stability within the relative standard measurements uncertainty of about 0.1% across all measurements. As the slight increase in spectral responsivity in the wavelength range from 300 nm to 350 nm in the third and fourth measurement compared to the first and second measurement occurs not only for TC3, but with almost identical spectral features also for TC4 and a well-known PTB reference detector which has been calibrated alongside as a cross-check, this increase is most likely due to a measurement artefact rather than due to temporal instability of the detectors' spectral responsivity. Note that the observed change is well within the stated measurement uncertainty. The results for TC1 and TC4 reveal almost identical temporal stability.

TC2's temporal stability in the wavelength range from 300 nm and above over the first three measurements is comparable to that of TC1, TC3 and TC4. Note that the third measurement in February 2026 was split into two: First, the spectral range 300 nm to 410 nm was measured, followed by the spectral range 200 nm to 300 nm. However, the fourth measurement in March 2026 revealed a significant degradation, not only in the spectral range 200 nm to 300 nm with a responsivity reduced by almost 25%, but also in the spectral range above 300 nm, which had previously been stable, by about 7%.

This instability of TC2 is most likely caused by irradiation from 200 nm to 280 nm in the second split of the third measurement. By considering $n = 3$ measurement repetitions at each wavelength (conducted at axial rotation angles 0° , 60° and 120°), estimating the exposure time $t = 4$ s and a beam diameter of $d = 2.6$ mm at the detector's sensitive area and using the known radiant power Φ_λ as shown in Fig. 2, the UV exposure H in the wavelength range

Figure 6: Comparison of the spectral responsivity over four consecutive measurements of detectors TC3 and TC2. For detector TC3, the relative deviation from the mean of all four measurements is shown. In contrast, for detector TC2, the relative deviation from the mean of the first three measurements is shown. The degradation of TC2 is most likely caused by irradiation in the wavelength range from 200 nm to 280 nm as outlined in Sect. 4.3.2.

200 nm to 280 nm can be approximated:

$$H = \sum_{\lambda=200 \text{ nm}}^{280 \text{ nm}} \frac{\Phi_{\lambda} \cdot t \cdot n}{\frac{\pi}{4} d^2} \approx 6.2 \text{ mJ} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2} \quad (4)$$

The degradation of silicon photodiodes due to UV irradiation is a well-known phenomenon [10, 11, 17]. Getz et al. provide an in-depth study of the UV stability of photodiodes in the chipS-CALe and S-CALe Up projects [14].

4.3.3 Temporal stability of TS2, TS3 and TS6

Fig. 7 shows a comparison of the spectral responsivity of detectors TS2, TS3 and TS6 over two consecutive measurements.

The spectral responsivity of detector TS2 shows a slight decrease at wavelengths equal to or longer than 220 nm, ranging from about 0.1 % to 0.3 %. This is significant compared to the relative standard measurement uncertainty realized in this wavelength range. Below 220 nm, the spectral responsivity differs more strongly between the two measurements, with both increased and decreased values measured. This scattering can most probably be explained by higher measurement uncertainty in this spectral range, compare Fig. 3. Overall, therefore, a slight degradation in the spectral responsivity of TS2 can be observed.

In contrast, TS3 shows a clear increase in spectral responsivity in the spectral range below 280 nm, up to about 1 %. From 280 nm and above, the spectral responsivity remains stable within the realised measurement uncertainty.

The same applies to TS6 for the entire studied spectral range. Its spectral responsivity remains stable at around 0.1 % to 0.2 %.

Figure 7: Comparison of the spectral responsivity over each two consecutive measurements with detectors TS2, TS3 and TS6. The relative deviation of the second from the first measurement is shown.

However, the interval between the first and second measurement was short for TS2, TS3 and TS6. Therefore, a more thorough assessment of temporal stability should be considered in future.

5 Conclusion

Several three-element reflection trap detectors with silicon photodiodes which were produced in the chipS-CALe and S-CALe Up projects have been set-up. Most of the photodiodes are so-called induced-junction photodiodes with reduced recombination losses, meant to serve as primary detector standards, so called Predictable Quantum Efficient Detectors (PQEDs).

These detectors have been calibrated in view of their spectral responsivity in the wavelength range from 200 nm to 410 nm against a cryogenic electrical substitution radiometer (CESR) facility at the Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB). PTB has recently updated this facility with a laser-driven light source for SI-traceable detector calibrations of the spectral responsivity in the UV wavelength range down to 200 nm.

- A comprehensive measurement uncertainty budget is presented, with typical relative standard measurement uncertainties in the range of about 0.1%. These highly accurate measurements have been performed in order to investigate the temporal stability of the photodiodes' spectral responsivity.
- It is revealed, that photodiodes produced in the chipS-CALe project are temporally stable in the wavelength range 280 nm to 410 nm within in the realised measurement uncertainty over a time frame of about 2 years.
- There is one induced-junction photodiode candidate (Wafer 44, see Tab. 1) among the photodiodes produced in the S-CALe Up project, which shows temporally stable spectral responsivity in the full spectral range 200 nm to 410 nm within the measurement uncertainty. However, this temporal stability was limited to a time period of two months; a more extended study should be considered.

To place the present results in context, long-term calibrations at PTB of three-element reflection trap detectors equipped with Hamamatsu S1337-1010 silicon photodiodes show a mean annual decrease in spectral responsivity of approximately 0.2% in the wavelength range from 220 nm to 370 nm. The photodiodes investigated here therefore exhibit very good temporal stability by comparison.

Furthermore, these precise calibrations of the spectral responsivity s_{meas} allow the derived key parameters of the photodiodes to be validated independently by comparing s_{meas} to the calculated spectral responsivity s_{calc} according to Eq. 2 for the first time in the UV spectral range [8].

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Author Contributions

Conceptualization, methodology and supervision: all authors; Photodiode development and fabrication: O.K., M.N.G; Photodiode packaging: E.B.; Detector housing design and setup: T.P.; Data acquisition and analysis: P.M., T.P., L.W.; Original manuscript: T.P., P.M.; Manuscript contributions: L.W., O.K., M.N.G., M.-M.S., J.G.; Project administration: J.G., L.W., T.P.

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are available upon reasonable request from the authors.

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Table 4: Measurement uncertainty budget for the first calibration of TS3 at 205 nm and 330 nm. Standard uncertainties in normal distribution are listed. $u_{\text{rel}}(x_i)$ is the relative contribution of x_i according to $\frac{\frac{\partial s}{\partial x_i} \cdot u(x_i)}{s(\lambda)}$.

X_i	$\lambda = 205 \text{ nm}$				$\lambda = 330 \text{ nm}$			
	x_i	$u(x_i)$	$ \frac{\partial s}{\partial x_i} \cdot u(x_i) / \frac{\text{A}}{\text{W}}$	$u_{\text{rel}}(x_i) / \%$	x_i	$u(x_i)$	$ \frac{\partial s}{\partial x_i} \cdot u(x_i) / \frac{\text{A}}{\text{W}}$	$u_{\text{rel}}(x_i) / \%$
Φ^{CESR}	0.3960 W	0.0004 W	$4.1 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.11	4.4758 W	0.0010 W	$5.7 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.02
U^{DUT}	0.1501 V	0.0003 V	$7.0 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.19	11.8863 V	0.0075 V	$1.7 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.06
$U^{\text{Mon-DUT}}$	0.0197 V	$< 0.0001 \text{ V}$	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-6}$	< 0.01	0.2733 V	$< 0.0001 \text{ V}$	$4.0 \cdot 10^{-6}$	< 0.01
$U^{\text{Mon-CESR}}$	0.0197 V	$< 0.0001 \text{ V}$	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-6}$	< 0.01	0.2726 V	$< 0.0001 \text{ V}$	$4.0 \cdot 10^{-6}$	< 0.01
R^{TIA}	$9.989 \cdot 10^6 \Omega$	$5.7 \cdot 10^3 \Omega$	$2.2 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.06	$9.989 \cdot 10^6 \Omega$	$5.7 \cdot 10^3 \Omega$	$1.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.06
F_{α}	0.9998	< 0.0001	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-6}$	< 0.01	0.9998	< 0.0001	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-6}$	< 0.01
F^{window}	0.9988	0.0005	$2.0 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.05	0.9994	0.0003	$8.6 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.03
$F_{\Delta\lambda}$	0.9997	0.0001	$5.3 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.01	1.0000	0.0001	$2.7 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.01
F_{O_2}	1.0015	0.0003	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.03	1.0000	< 0.0001	$< 0.1 \cdot 10^{-8}$	< 0.01
F_{SR}	1	0.0004	$1.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.04	1	0.0004	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.04
F_{ϕ}	1	0.0002	$5.7 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.02	1	0.0002	$4.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.02
F_{λ}	0.9969	0.0038	$1.4 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.38	1.0000	0.0001	$2.8 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.01
$F^{\text{non-uni}}$	1	< 0.0001	$7.6 \cdot 10^{-7}$	< 0.01	1	< 0.0001	$5.3 \cdot 10^{-6}$	< 0.01
F_T	1	0.0001	$4.2 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.01	1	< 0.0001	$5.3 \cdot 10^{-6}$	< 0.01
$u_{\text{c,rel}}(s(\lambda)) / \%$	0.45				0.10			